

A highly sensitive extractive spectrophotometric determination of zirconium(IV) using 2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran

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Abstract : An extractive spectrophotometric method is developed for the microdetermination of zirconium(IV) based on the formation of a dark yellow complex by its reaction with 2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (FHB). The 1 : 4 (metal : ligand) complex can be extracted into benzene in the pH range of 6.7-7.3, whose absorbance is measured at 420 nm. The proposed system is simple, fast, highly reproducible with a relative standard deviation of 0.25% and has been applied satisfactorily to the analysis of several samples including flue dust and water samples.

Keywords : Spectrophotometric determination, zirconium(IV).

In continuation of our work on the spectroscopic determination of metal ions, in the present communication an attempt has been made to introduce a new chromone derivative, 2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (FHB) for the complexation and extractive spectrophotometric determination of zirconium which not only gives a very high sensitivity ($\epsilon \approx 10^5$) but also offers the advantages of high selectivity and rapidity as compared to most of the existing methods¹.

Results and discussion

Effect of nature of alkalis and pH on the absorbance of Zr^{IV} complex : It was observed that zirconium in its tetravalent state reacted with FHB forming a yellow complex in weakly acidic medium. The intensity of the coloured species increased on decreasing the acidity of the solution with aqueous ammonia (pH 6.7-7.3), which was quantitatively extracted into benzene. The presence of FHB prevented the precipitation of Zr^{IV} as its hydroxide at this pH. The influence of different alkalis on the extraction of the complex was similarly seen at pH 6.7-7.3. The absorbance was found to be maximum (0.570) with aqueous ammonia used for adjusting pH, whereas a decreasing trend in extraction was observed in case of NaHCO₃ (0.550), Na₂CO₃ (0.450) and NaOH (0.210) solution. The effect of pH (adjusted with 1 M aqueous ammonia) on extraction showed that the optimum value for achieving quantitative recovery of the complex was 6.7-7.3.

Effect of various organic solvents on the absorbance of Zr^{IV} complex : Though the complex showed extractability into different organic water immiscible solvents up to different extent namely benzene, dichloromethane, 1,2-dichloroethane, carbon tetrachloride, ethyl acetate and amyl acetate; benzene was found to be the most suitable as it gave maximum and constant absorbance (> 75 min) of the complex. A single extraction with an equal volume (10 ml) of the solvent was sufficient to transfer the metal ion quantitatively to the organic layer.

λ_{max} and stability of the complex : The absorption spectrum of the dark yellow complex indicated that the maximum lied in the range 415-425 nm in the visible region, where the reagent blank had minimal absorbance. In benzene, the absorbance remained unchanged for more than 75 min.

The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 0.7-1.3 ml of FHB (0.1% in ethanol), 20-60 °C temperature range of aqueous phase and 15-240 s equilibration time for $\leq 9 \mu\text{g Zr}^{\text{IV}}$ per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). The order of addition of various solutions should be the same as per proposed procedure.

The metal complex obeyed Beer's law in the range 0-0.9 $\mu\text{g Zr}^{\text{IV}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$. However, the optimum range which could be measured accurately from Ringbom plot was 0.17-0.63 ppm of zirconium. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the system were $1.04 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.00088 \mu\text{g Zr}^{\text{IV}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of the Zr-complex

pH ^a	5.0	5.6	6.0	6.2	6.5	6.7-7.3	7.4	7.9
Absorbance	0.080	0.140	0.220	0.450	0.530	0.570	0.545	0.510
0.1% FHB (ml) ^b	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7-1.3	1.4	1.5	1.7
Absorbance	0.000	0.380	0.510	0.540	0.570	0.550	0.520	0.490
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	5	10	15-90				
Absorbance	0.120	0.525	0.560	0.570				

^aZr^{IV} = 5 µg, 0.1% FHB = 1 ml, pH (with 1 M aqueous ammonia) = variable, equilibration time = 30 s, solvent = benzene, aqueous phase = organic phase = 10 ml, No. of extractions = 1; ^bpH = 6.7-7.3, other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in FHB concentration, also *b* = 2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran; ^c0.1% FHB in ethanol = 1 ml, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

metal to ligand ratio in the extracted species was determined by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper² and was found to be 1 : 4 which was further confirmed by the mole ratio and equilibrium shift methods³.

Effect of diverse ions : For 5 µg Zr^{IV} per 10 ml aqueous phase, the anions and complexing agents (mg amounts of sodium or potassium salts in parentheses) such as iodide, sulfate, nitrate, thiourea and sulfosalicylic acid (100 each); carbonate (80); chloride, bromide, fluoride, dithionite, thiocyanate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (50 each); acetate and oxalate (20 each); nitrite and ascorbic acid (10 each); citrate (5); tartrate (1) and glycerol (1 ml) were without effect. However, phosphate, disodium EDTA and H₂O₂ even in traces interfered seriously. In 10 ml aqueous volume containing 5 µg zirconium(IV), Co^{II} and Mg^{II} (10 each); Ni^{II}, Hg^{II}, Al^{III} and Ca^{II} (5 each); Se^{IV} (2.5); Be^{II} (2); Mn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Os^{VIII} and Ag^I (1 each); Ti^{IV} (0.5); Sb^{III}, V^V, Cr^{VI}, W^{VI} and U^{VI} (0.1 each); Pt^{IV}, Pd^{II}, Mo^{VI}, Nb^V and Ta^V (0.05 each); Ir^{III}, Au^{III} and Ru^{III} (0.01 each) were without effect. In these cases either the elements were not precipitated as hydroxides in presence of FHB or if precipitated, they did not affect the absorbance of Zr-FHB complex as the precipitates remained at the interface after shaking with the solvent and were retained in the separatory funnel alongwith the aqueous phase. Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Cr^{III}, Th^{IV}, Sn^{II}, Bi^{III}, Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} did not interfere in presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure. However, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} interfered seriously giving higher results.

Experimental

A standard stock solution of zirconium containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount (0.3533 g) of ZrOCl₂.8H₂O in 2 M HCl to give 100 ml solution and standardized

gravimetrically by precipitation with ammonia and ignition to ZrO₂⁴. Solutions of other metal ions were prepared by dissolving their commonly available salts (A.R.) in deionized water or dilute acids to obtain ≤ 10 mg ml⁻¹ of the ion. A 1 M solution of aqueous ammonia was prepared from the available 8.6 M ammonia solution (NICE 'LR'). 2-(2'-Furyl)-3-hydroxy-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (FHB) (m.p. 171 °C) was synthesized by the literature method⁵ and dissolved in ethanol to give 0.1% (w/v) solution. Benzene (Ranbaxy) was used as such for extraction. A UV-Vis (Shimadzu 140-02) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cells was used for absorbance measurements and spectral studies.

Solutions of sample mixtures and flue dust were prepared as in the earlier one⁶ using zirconium(IV) in place of tungsten(VI). To an aliquot (0.5 ml) of flue dust solution, FHB was added followed by 20 mg thiourea to suppress Cu^{II} present in the sample and aqueous ammonia to adjust pH 6.7. Any precipitate of Fe(OH)₃ was filtered and zirconium was determined from the filtrate by the proposed method. Tap water sample (1000 ml) was spiked with 25 µg Zr^{IV}, evaporated to about 25 ml, treated with 6% H₂O₂ (w/v) (1-2 ml) in ammonical medium and heated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in dilute HCl and volume of the solution was made to 25 ml. An aliquot (5 ml) of this solution was taken and adjusted to pH 6.7 after adding FHB. The precipitate of Fe(OH)₃ were removed and zirconium was determined from the filtrate as per the proposed procedure.

Procedure : To a sample solution containing ≤ 9 µg of zirconium(IV) and other metal ions were added 0.1% (w/v) FHB in ethanol (1 ml), sufficient deionized water and adjusted the pH at 6.7-7.3 with 1 M aqueous ammonia in a final 10 ml aqueous volume. It was then equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of benzene in a separatory funnel for 30 s. After phase separation, the dark yellow organic layer was poured over anhydrous

sodium sulphate for removal of any retained water and the absorbance was measured at 420 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank. The amount of zirconium was determined from a calibration curve constructed by taking zirconium ($0-0.9 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) as per the proposed procedure.

For the samples containing up to 1 mg of Ba^{II} , 5 mg sodium citrate; up to 1 mg of Sr^{II} , 1 mg sodium potassium tartrate; up to 1 mg of Cr^{III} , 10 mg ascorbic acid; up to 0.1 mg of Th^{IV} and 0.05 mg of Sn^{II} , 50 mg sodium fluoride in each case, had been necessitated to mask them just before effecting extraction with the solvent. Up to 0.5 mg of Bi^{III} and 0.1 mg of Cu^{II} could be masked with 100 mg each of potassium iodide and thiourea, respectively at pH 6.7. Interference due to Fe^{III} (up to 0.4 mg) was removed by precipitating it as $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ by adding aqueous ammonia in presence of FHB at pH 6.7 where Zr^{IV} was not coprecipitated. In all these cases, the extraction of the complex was carried out at the same pH (6.7).

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